

COMMUNICATIVE AND COGNATE STRATEGIES IN MASS-MEDIA

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Abstract: *While a great amount of literature has focused on the relationship between communication strategies and corporate reputation, there is no systematic research on the different kinds of social media communication strategies. This article describes and analyzes about communicative and cognate strategies in mass-media.*

Keywords: *communicative strategies, cognate strategies, mass-media*

Mass media refers to a diverse array of [media technologies](#) that reach a large audience via [mass communication](#). The technologies through which this communication takes place include a variety of outlets. [Broadcast media](#) transmit information electronically via media such as [films](#), [radio](#), recorded music, or [television](#). [Digital media](#) comprises both [Internet](#) and [mobile](#) mass communication. [Internet](#) media comprise such services as [email](#), [social media](#) sites, [websites](#), and Internet-based radio and television. Many other mass media outlets have an additional presence on the web, by such means as linking to or running TV ads online, or distributing [QR codes](#) in outdoor or print media to direct mobile users to a website. In this way, they can use the easy accessibility and outreach capabilities the Internet affords, as thereby easily broadcast information throughout many different regions of the world simultaneously and cost-efficiently. Outdoor media transmit information via such media as [AR advertising](#); [billboards](#); [blimps](#); flying billboards (signs in tow of airplanes); placards or kiosks placed inside and outside buses, commercial buildings, shops, sports stadiums, subway cars, or trains; signs; or [skywriting](#). Print media transmit information via physical objects, such as [books](#), [comics](#), [magazines](#), [newspapers](#), or [pamphlets](#). Event organising and [public speaking](#) can also be considered forms of mass media.

Mass media is a channel for people to know the disaster-related information which is happening in which disaster is news that related to human interest. Disaster news contains high news value so that the media are competing against the disaster news. Media information besides needed by the disaster victims for sharing the information of various emergency action. Strategy is an overall plan in reaching the target even though there is no guarantee of the success. The term of

strategy is widely used in the military world, but in many other fields it is also used even in different ways. In the communication study, strategy means a comprehensive plan in achieving the goal of communication effectiveness, so that messages conveyed the communicators give effect as expected, especially the changes in the communicant's attitudes, behavior, mindset and views to something. The purpose of communication in this case may vary depending on the communications field, for example in the context of disaster management is instructional communication that has the goal of achieving interactive educational process on the communicant side.

Basically, humans in the delivering the messages besides using verbal code (spoken and written language) also use nonverbal code. Nonverbal codes are often called sign languages or silent languages. Onong Uchjana Effendy suggests that communication will fail if there is a discrepancy between verbal messages which are delivered with visible nonverbal messages. Albert Mahrabian as quoted Hafied Cangara states that the confidence level of people's conversation only 7 percent comes from verbal language, 38 percent of vocal sound and 55 percent of facial expression (nonverbal). He also adds that if there is a conflict between what a person says and his actions, then others tend to believe things that are nonverbal. Meanwhile, Mark Knapp mentions that the use of nonverbal code in communicating has the following functions:

- 1) Reassure what it says (repetition).
- 2) Showing feelings and emotions that cannot be expressed by words (substitution).
- 3) Showing the identity so that others can know it
- 4) Adding or completing the utterances that are perceived as imperfect.

In the presenting the message it is known a technique of managing one-sided issue and two sided issue. The research about the technique of managing the messages like this was conducted in an experiment by Hovland, Lumsdein and Sheffield. From the experiment it was concluded that the one sided issue method is only suitable for low educated audiences and they already know the information earlier so that its function is only to reinforce the existing information. The messaging strategy described above is relevant for all forms of communication, whether it is interpersonal communication, group communication or mass communication. In this case D.W. Johnson, says that there are three criteria that must be met until the communication can be effective, namely: (1) messages sent must be easily understood by the communicant, (2) the message sender must have credibility in the eyes of the recipient and (3) the communicator must try to get the

feedback optimally about the effect of the message on the communicant. Another opinion expressed by A.W.Widjaja, the message should be submitted appropriately, like aiming and shooting what comes out should be in accordance with the target. The message must meet the requirements of: a) The message must be general, b) The message must be communicated clearly not vague, c) The message should be conveyed in clear and compatible language to the communicant, the local situation and the conditions in which it communicates, and) The message should be delivered in a positive form, e) The message should be delivered in a balanced manner. f) The message should be tailored to the wishes of the communicant. Indonesian communication expert Onong Uchjana Effendy, says that the message should be achieved as follows: a) the message should be arranged and submitted in such a way so that it foster the audience's interest, b) the message must use the communication symbols that can be understood by the communicant, c) the message can grow the personal needs of communicant and suggests several ways to meet the needs that arises in the communicant, d) the messages should be able to suggest various ways of solving problems that can be done by the communicant.

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